

The Prospects and Challenges of Utilizing Artificial Intelligence in Vocational Education in the 21st Century in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the prospects and challenges of utilizing artificial intelligence in vocational education in the 21st century in Nigeria. The prospects and challenges of utilizing artificial intelligence were elaborately discussed. The paper analyzed Artificial Intelligence Initiatives for Vocational Education in Nigeria. The study identified learning, teaching, administrative, personalized learning experience, teachers and artificial intelligence work together and universal learning as prospects of artificial intelligence and policy, techno-economic, security and related issues as challenges of utilizing artificial intelligence in vocational education in Nigeria. The paper also discussed the future of Artificial Intelligence in Vocational Education in Nigeria. The study concluded that the use of artificial intelligence is a positive thing in spite of the challenges. The study suggested Federal government's formulation of a comprehensive national blueprint to guide the use of Artificial Intelligence strategy by involving key Nigerian institutions, academia, private and public sectors stakeholders in its conception, develop a Strict compliance to ethical use policies of Artificial Intelligence for teaching and learning activities in institutions in Nigeria, transparency and integrity in the use of Artificial Intelligence systems enforcement and relevant policies to curtail excesses arising from the use of Artificial Intelligence for individuals and education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Prospects, Challenges, Utilization, Artificial, Intelligence, Vocational Education, Century, Nigeria

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is gradually revolutionizing several sectors, including healthcare, education, energy, agriculture, finance and manufacturing, among others. Artificial Intelligence has impacted education as a teaching and learning process for knowledge and skills acquisition by individuals and groups, with varying degrees of outcomes. To ensure inclusive and equitable quality education whilst promoting lifelong learning opportunities in line with the Sustainable Development Goal four, we must promote AI for educational activities in developing countries. Artificial Intelligence is a technology that is rapidly spreading throughout many industries, and vocational education is no exception. Artificial Intelligence is quickly becoming a popular tool in classrooms and schools around the world. In fact, 92% of institutions are already using Artificial Intelligence technology regularly (Julia, 2024). Artificial Intelligence in vocational education takes on many forms and can be used by anyone involved in an academic setting, such as teachers, students, and administrative members. Artificial intelligence in education can be used in the classroom for any age group, making this an exciting and evolving technology. Artificial Intelligence also known as machine intelligence and refers to the simulated human intelligence in computer systems and programs or in machines. For example, Apple's Siri and Google's Alexa both use voice recognition powered by artificial intelligence.

Artificial Intelligence is the development of intelligence structure or mechanism in a organization that serves as decision support system in some cases, or situations that make decisions as a replacement or supplement to employees of the organizations (Agha et al., 2014). Agha et al (2014) argue that the primary aim of artificial intelligence is to supplement human brain in decision making and implementation. Liebowitz (2006) listed the following areas where artificial intelligence can be applied. These include expert/knowledge-based systems, case-based reasoning, speech recognition and understanding, natural language processing, robotics usages, computer vision, neural networking, generic algorithms, and hybrid intelligent systems. This means that organizations can use artificial intelligence strategies to enhance information capturing, synthesizing, organizing, knowledge sharing and information dissemination (Agha et al., 2014; Liebowitz, 2006). The artificial intelligence strategies are object-oriented languages. They includes Small Talk, C++, Java and Visual Basic. Software is developed here to: specify the problem; analyze the problem; design the algorithm to solve problem; implement the algorithm; test and verify the completed program; maintain and update the program etc. These are computers of very high speed operations, they perform multiple tasks and have artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is the term used to link human behavior and characteristics in man-made machines (Otuka, Akande & Iginla, 2012). Artificial Intelligence is the act of scientists building machines that imitate, speak, have emotions and reason in the same method in which humans do. The method by which computers imitate human intelligence is called knowledge information processing system (KIPS). Examples of artificial intelligence Languages computers are the Wallet PC, Virtual Reality, Linus Watch, Wearable PC, Ballistic Translator, PUMA, COG, DANTE, WABOT-2, HELPMATE etc. Another example is the Scripting Computer Language. The scripting computer language is a programming language that is used to manipulate, customize, and automate the facilities of existing system. A Scripting language is a programming language that employs a high-level construct to interpret and execute one command at a time. A scripting computer language executes tasks within a special run-time environment by an interpreter instead of a compiler (Odudimu & Ajao, 2004). Examples are Java script-The most popular scripting language, PHP-General Purpose Scripting Computer Language etc.

Vocational education is that part of the total experience whereby the individual learns knowledge and skills successfully to carry on a gainful occupation. Vocational education is also seen as a highly useful education, because its occupational content offers one the opportunity to acquire skills, attitudes, interests and knowledge to perform socially and economically work that is beneficial to the individual and the society (Ugboaja, 2016). Okon and Uke (2015), posited that the progress of a nation is the function of the level of the resourcefulness of the people which to a greater extent, relate to the level of quality of vocational training and purposeful development of functional education in that nation. Vocational education adequately equip students to be more effective in this age of science and technology, and to raise a generation of people who can think for themselves and respect the dignity of labour and propel its citizenry into a vibrant economy. What is needed today and tomorrow are workers with good technical skill background, rugged enough to transform Nigeria into positive technological breakthrough with the ability to meet its immediate demand. As the world around us is changing fast, there must be an increased emphasis on vocational education in meeting the aims and objectives in which it was established (Dimkpa & James, 2020). Agwi, (2019) opined that the enterprise of manpower development is practicalized on the transfer of knowledge and skills to the trainee through education and training. Efficient and corruption free educational systems are essential component of this, for cultural, self-economic and

environmentally sustainable development of individual communities and nations. Thus any country which desires to enhance and accelerates its manpower and national development must take its vocational educational system seriously and execute it comprehensively. Vocational education is important to the development of human resources, impartation of appropriate skills, knowledge and attitudes. It is the basis for transformation, industrialization and a high way to global knowledge economy. It leads to national transformation and ensuring of peace and security. Thus, the goals of wealth creation, employment generation, poverty reduction and value re-orientation can only be attained and sustained through an efficient vocational education system which impacts the relevant skills, knowledge, capacities, attitudes and values. The scope of its contributions cut across mechanical technology, automobile technology, wood work technology, electrical and electronic technology, building technology etc. When vocational education program succeeds, even a non entity will observe it, and when it is failing, it will be observed also (Dimkpa & James, 2020).

According to Okoro (2006) Vocational Education is defined as any form of education whose primary purpose is to prepare persons for employment in recognized occupations. Vocational education provides the skills, knowledge and attitudes necessary for effective employment in specific occupation. Any education that is necessary for effective employment in an occupation is referred to as Vocational education. Vocational education is education designed to prepare individuals or skilled personnel for one or a group of occupations, trader or jobs (Egumu, Akpotohwo & Ogeibiri, 2017). Vocational education is provided in special programmes offered at secondary and post-secondary levels. Vocational education is expensive education because of the tools, equipment and materials that are part of the training process. To avoid the wastage of resources, learners for Vocational education should be carefully selected to ensure that they have the interest and aptitude to benefit from the training. Those learners having the genuine interest for the occupation only that should be trained. Establishment of vocational education programmes should therefore be based on needs, the needs of the country; the needs of the community; and the needs of the individual citizens. Vocational education programmes should therefore be evaluated to find answers to the following questions: Are the individuals trained in the programme able to find employment in the occupation in which they have been trained? Are they doing well in their place of employment? etc. The 21st century is the era we are in now. Century is a time of freedom, technology advancement and a digital world.

Artificial Intelligence Initiatives for Vocational Education in Nigeria

There is no universally acceptable definition of AI in the literature. However, a comprehensive definition of AI refers to computing systems that can engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correction and use of data for complex processing tasks. The underlying concept of AI presupposes the creation of intelligent machines capable of learning from their environment (via data collection and analysis) and replicating tasks hitherto attributed to humans. As such, Artificial Intelligence offers a way to surmount constraints associated with traditional teaching and learning methods and invariably, improve access to quality. The citizenry needs to leverage AI to bridge the literacy gap and subsequently, achieve the Sustainable Development Goal four. Though major industry players such as Google, International Business Machine and Facebook have established AI research centres in Africa with the aim of advancing the knowledge of AI on the continent, local initiatives like Deep Learning Indaba, the African Institute for Mathematical Science (AIMS), Data Science Africa, Women+ in Machine Learning and Data Science (WIMLDS) and others have been strengthening the knowledge of AI in Africa (Julia, 2024). For instance, the African Institute for Mathematical Scientists (AIMS) in Rwanda, in

partnership with Facebook and Google, offers a one-year master's programme in AI which aims at equipping graduate students with basic research skills in AI to respond to the present and future needs of Africa. Similarly, Data Science Nigeria (DSN) is an initiative which aims at training one million AI talents in the next 10 years. In 2019, DSN published a learning resource aimed at upscaling the skills of primary school learners in data science and AI. While these initiatives have contributed to the growth of the nascent AI industry in Africa and subsequently, set the pace for AI revolution in Africa, little success has been recorded in the application of AI for education in Africa compared to developed regions. Though local initiatives such as M-Shule, Daptio, Tuteria and others have enhanced teaching and learning activities of students in Sub-Saharan Africa to some extent through their mobile learning and tutoring platforms, massive investment in AI for education is required to enable Africa leverage AI for the education of its teeming population.

Prospects of Artificial Intelligence for Vocational Education in Nigeria

Artificial Intelligence is currently progressing at an accelerated pace, and this already impacts on the profound nature of services within higher education. The adoption and use of Artificial intelligence for education in Nigeria is still at the early stage. Integrating AI capabilities into the education system brings greater benefits to teachers and students alike, allowing for a more personalized academic path, better results and better prepared individuals. The following are prospects for teaching, learning, administration and individual usage in the application of Artificial Intelligence for vocational education in Nigeria:

1. Learning prospects

Artificial Intelligence allows smart learning as Nigerian students can have personalized learning instructions in their areas of interests. With the aid of Artificial Intelligence, homework and classes could be customized based on student's aptitudes, needs and interests, while their overall performance in the assessments could be analyzed to determine relevant resources to help students understand the assigned tasks. Artificial Intelligence plays a vital role of a personalized learning resource allocator for students, helping teachers focus more on facilitation, while technology handles the intricacies of teaching and learning assessment and resource distribution. Apart from allowing students to learn at their own pace, there is a diverse learning options, some of which may also tackle learning disabilities. The use of AI such as Tutoring Software, robots and humanoids has shown benefits in enhancing the learning experience of students with Autistic Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Similarly, Immersive Reader is an AI service which enhances reading and comprehension through text decoding solutions for students with learning differences such as dyslexia. Artificial Intelligence also reinforces students' learning by combining technology interface with face-to-face interaction as blended learning. Before the advent of AI and other modern instructional technologies, learning in educational institutions was predominantly based on physical interaction between instructors and students. Though this traditional model was effective in educating limited number of students at a given time, constraints such as geographical barriers, limited space and time difference must be resolved to get the best experience out of such learning exercise. Application of AI tools could remove barriers associated with conventional learning methods and recreate unique classroom experience for reinforced learning activities. Blended learning is richer for many reasons, for instance in allowing for diversity in learning pathways and reinforcing learning sessions. Blended learning combines the online delivery of educational content with the best features of classroom interaction and live instruction in such a way as to personalize learning, allow thoughtful reflection, and differentiate instruction from student to student across a diverse group of learners. Additionally, AI provides a means to build a learning community. AI

applications that allow participant interaction create a platform to build relationships that could enhance learning, for instance study groups across different educational systems. With the aid of AI, participants in educational programmes could engage in group discussions, share resources and collaborate on ideas to advance their knowledge on different topics. AI support online collaborative learning discussions among students by using academically productive talk moves. AI applications could also assist Nigerian students to monitor conversations in many groups using recording devices and link them with more experienced colleagues, thus fostering peer mentoring within the learning community. It provides marginalized people and communities, people with disabilities, refugees, those out of school, and those living in isolated communities with access to appropriate learning opportunities. With the advancement in AI, Nigerian students can have access to personalized instruction in real-time with adequate feedback (synchronous learning) and as self-paced interaction with flexible schedules (asynchronous learning). Artificial Intelligence could also advance quality education with highly personalized teaching programs for all ages across the world. Although still relatively expensive, AI costs will eventually fall with industry competition, as we have seen with telecommunication.

2. Teaching prospects

Artificial Intelligence has given flexibility to teachers in Nigerian vocational education institutions. Depending on the specific technology, using AI could reduce the burden of attending classrooms, marking papers and other tasks, enhancing the overall teaching experience and quality. The use of AI could assist teachers in identifying the learning needs and abilities of individual students and developing appropriate measures to respond to such needs. Also, teacher-facing AI systems are used to support the teacher and reduce workload by automating tasks such as administration, assessment, feedback, and plagiarism detection. Artificial Intelligence could also provide additional support for teachers in analyzing students' data, predicting their academic achievements and proffering solutions to address their learning challenges. Importantly, AI helps educators have greater insight as to how students are progressing. This means that they could adjust their approach, supporting students' individual needs. The use of AI could provide Nigerian teachers with adequate information on unique attributes of individual students which could influence their career paths. Nigerian teachers could also leverage AI capabilities to build learning communities with their colleagues. In addition, AI could foster the development of smart content and platforms for professional development of teachers. Peers and mentors may emerge from such communities, invariably boosting teaching experience and quality including AI mentors for learners, and development for educators through virtual global conferences. Teachers see the same advantages as students, but they see it from a different perspective. For example, just as students use AI learning apps to work on their weaknesses and topics they struggle with, teachers can use this information to understand how to better the focus on their lessons. It is no secret that younger generations like to spend a lot of time on devices like phones or tablets. Learning through AI-powered apps is a more fun way to study both inside and outside the classroom, making it easier for teachers to engage their students. The more schools, educators, and students continue to use AI, the smarter it will become. As schools and educators see what students are interested in learning based on interactions with apps and programs, they will have an easier time developing curriculum and course materials.

3. Make Administrative Tasks Simpler prospects

Artificial Intelligence can help teachers with their administrative tasks, leaving them more time to focus on preparing lessons and teaching. Tasks like grading exams can be sped up by using AI technology and software that helps teachers streamline this normally long process.

It's not only teachers that benefit from artificial intelligence in education. Other administrative staff can turn to AI to help with admissions and classifying large amounts of paperwork, as well.

4. Personalized Learning Experience prospects

We are used everything from addition to suggested content presented to us based on our personal preferences. When it comes to education, AI is doing the same thing. Not all the students in a classroom learn at the same level as their peers, so by using AI to do things like personalized assignments or even exam questions, each student gets the same course material catered to their abilities. For example, software such as Carnegie Learning is being used by students from elementary school to college. This program uses AI to provide feedback on assignments as well as personalized testing and learning.

5. Teachers and Artificial Intelligence Work Together prospects

It is difficult for a single teacher to provide the same level of care and attention to each individual student in the classroom. However, together with Artificial Intelligence, teachers can now address the needs of individual students more efficiently. The examples we have already seen, such as simplifying administrative tasks and using specialized software to offer a personalized learning experience, saves time for teachers. In spite all the technological advancements, machines cannot do it all. The extra time teachers have due to Artificial Intelligence learning can then be better used to provide more individualized attention to a greater number of students.

6. More Universal Learning prospects

Students learn at different levels, but they also have different needs and backgrounds. In a single classroom, you might have students who speak different native languages or have impairments or disabilities that make the way they learn unique. Artificial Intelligence helps to bridge the gap between these students by offering programs and software, such as Presentation Translator, that can translate a presentation or course material. This makes learning more accessible to a wider number of students, including those with hearing or visual disabilities.

Challenges of Artificial Intelligence in Vocational Education in Nigeria

In spite of the enormous benefits of AI in education, there are some challenges bedeviling the application of AI for education in Nigeria. Stefania (2023) grouped the challenges into three interwoven categories as policy, techno-economic and security:

1. Policy challenges

There is far-reaching policy change which stakeholders in Nigeria needs to address to successfully incorporate AI in teaching and learning. A comprehensive policy framework, much of which would require overhaul of current policies and creation of new ones, is a prerequisite for fostering participation by industry players and for achieving a sustainable environment where the application of AI of education will thrive. Besaw and Filitiz (2023) suggest that delivering the promise of positive AI will require good systems of governance, which constitute part of the policy framework. In expressing the need for appropriate AI policies for education, educators must see AI as instrumental to their institution's competitiveness, yet most institutions still lack a formal data strategy to advance AI. Even though, most African countries have ICT policies that are being implemented effectively, there is still a dearth of AI policies in Nigeria. In comparison to Europe, Canada, the U.S., and China, there is no well-documented strategy for AI in Nigeria. While we can learn from other regions, we cannot import policies that may not fit the context of African societies. Thus, relevant policies which will create clear directions on the application of AI for education in line with the peculiarities of the African continent need to be developed.

2. Techno-economic challenges

The optimization of AI for education requires an environment with adequate infrastructure, state-of-the-art data facilities and requisite AI expertise, which are largely inadequate in Nigeria. Extremely inconsistent Information Technology infrastructure represents a major challenge that needs to be addressed by various Nigerian governments and the private sector mostly because AI requires robust networks, immense computing power, and stable connections. The absence of sufficient technical infrastructures, AI skills and data gaps as well as poor regulatory environments for these limits the application of AI for education in Nigeria. This often results in intellectual and financial advantage to some countries, communities and people over others at least in the short-term. Driven by technology and finance, the more educated and financially buoyancy will have early and better access to AI.

3. Security and related data Issues challenges

While Artificial Intelligence offers enormous benefits to teaching and learning, its proper functioning relies on the collection and analysis of personal data of students and faculty members in educational programmes. The collection of such confidential information raises serious issues of privacy and data protection. Safety and security issues regarding AI-based systems revolve around concepts such as safe AI for use by humans, verification, validation, self-awareness in adversary prone environments etc. As AI systems becomes more integrated into teaching and learning, participants of educational programmes will be more exposed to unintended risks as other people could gain unauthorized access to their private lives, among other potential problems. In addition, , since AI relies on data, its outcome and subsequent use are as good as the data put into it. Where the given data provides for a chance of having a misleading outcome, there is a high chance that AI could bring about serious problems to that effect. The wrong information given to the system can cause a lot of damages. For instance a situation where Artificial Intelligence robot mistakenly lifted human into a pepper grinding machine and grinded him is a disaster. A robot positioned to sell in the supermarket could malfunction to destroy everything in the supermarket etc.

The future of Artificial Intelligence in Vocational Education in Nigeria

Artificial intelligence in vocational education is not going anywhere. Its presence in the classroom and in schools is only going to increase, so that it ideal to get on board is sooner rather than later. While we cannot know exactly how artificial intelligence in vocational education will grow, we can make certain predictions based on how it is already used. The way Artificial Intelligence is used now will be fine-tuned and made more accurate as the technology becomes more developed. For instance, the way students learn with Artificial Intelligence applications will become more sophisticated and detailed to be able to analyze data more effectively and creating more personalized experience for students. Aside from AI apps, virtual reality games and software are likely to become more predominant in classrooms. Virtual reality AI can allow students to get first-hand experience, which makes learning easier and more interactive. Science experiments can be performed with such technologies, making a safer and more engaging environment for students. For schools, AI will be used to create smart classrooms and smart buildings. Already we have the technology where things like temperature, alarms, and lights are controlled remotely by AI-powered apps. Using this technology in schools can turn buildings into both more secure environments for students and more efficient to manage for administration.

Artificial Intelligence will be helpful for everyone involved in vocational education. The focus of any educational institution is its students, there is undisputed fact that AI is a powerful tool that has the ability to make everyone's lives easier, but it is particularly suited for students. With AI

programs and apps, students can choose to learn anywhere and at any time by logging in at their convenience. Furthermore, with apps that provide immediate feedback or function like a virtual teacher, students do not need to wait long period of time between learning sessions. These virtual teachers cannot replace a real human teaching, but it can help students track their progress more instantly, encouraging them to be more active in their own education.

Additionally, due to the nature of AI and its ability to adapt and personalize content for each user, students are able to practice more self-directed learning and work on subjects or topics that they struggle with. For example, if a student uses an AI-powered app to prepare for an exam and they often make the same mistake on a single topic, the app will consistently provide more exercises until the students gets a better understanding of their mistakes and how to correct it.

Conclusion

The use of Artificial Intelligence in vocational education is nothing to be afraid of. The use of artificial intelligence is a positive thing. Artificial Intelligence is a highly advanced tool that can be used to make teaching and learning easier and more accessible for students and teachers at all levels. With these new technologies, students have the abilities and morale to take education into their own hands with more personalized learning at any time they like with individualized learning done at a students' convenience. This is why learning methods are entirely based on distance learning where students can get personal attention in small classrooms and earn to bag a degree while studying at their own pace. Modern computer languages have made the understanding of codes, operating systems and programs of computer easy for use. As more technological innovations occurs, more computer languages will come to play, the operation and understanding of computer will become more easy for man. Artificial Intelligence unarguably holds the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning in Nigeria by eradicating challenges associated with conventional educational methods. The application of AI in teaching and learning has come to stay, and Nigeria will likely leverage AI to achieve its educational goals, including enhanced knowledge acquisition in the classroom settings and at home.

However, AI successes have been observed with some perceived risks, disruptive tendencies, and negative impacts. These risks could undermine the benefits of AI for education in Nigeria and threatened the development of the Nigeria nascent Artificial Intelligence industry, if not monitored properly. Currently, there are local initiatives which could transform the AI landscape in Nigeria through the development of exciting talents and world-class AI solutions capable of meeting the needs of the continent in the nearest future. A robust collaboration among AI startups, researchers, policy makers, industry players, educational institutions and government agencies is required to realize the full benefits of AI for vocational education in Nigeria. Invariably, AI has the capability to enrich teaching and learning experience in Africa, thus fostering the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goal four.

Recommendations

Considering the sensitive nature of Artificial Intelligence technology for ethical, effectiveness and efficient usage, the author suggests the following:

1. Nigerian government should formulate a comprehensive national blueprint to guide the use of Artificial Intelligence strategy by involving key Nigerian institutions, academia, private and public sectors stakeholders in its conception.
2. Develop a Strict compliance to ethical use policies of Artificial Intelligence for teaching and learning activities in institutions in Nigeria.

3. Transparency and integrity in the use of Artificial Intelligence systems should be enforced by Federal Government.
4. Formulate relevant policies to curtail excesses arising from the use of Artificial Intelligence for individuals in Nigeria.

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